

FIGURE S1. Morphospace of limb proportions constructed from the species averages of the reduced set of variables. Abbreviations: J, jumping; LAC, last common ancestor of frog-like salientians; NA, locomotor mode unknown, used for fossil taxa and LAC; Sw, swimming; WH, walking-hopping.

FIGURE S2. Detail of morphospace occupation during the (A) Jurassic, (B) Paleogene, (C-D) Early Cretaceous, and (E-F) Late Cretaceous. Morphospace constructed from the total set of variables.

FIGURE S3. Detail of morphospace occupation during the (A-B) Jurassic, (C-D) Early Cretaceous, (E-F) Late Cretaceous, and (G-H) Paleogene. Morphospace constructed from the reduced set of variables.

FIGURE S4. Phylomorphospace of limb proportions constructed from the species averages of the full set of variables.

FIGURE S5. Phylomorphospace of limb proportions constructed from the species averages of the reduced set of variables.

FIGURE S6. Ancestral state reconstruction of PC1 for extant species shown as coloured branches. PC1 values derived from the PCA of the total dataset. Coloured bars at the tips represent the locomotor mode of each species. Abbreviations: J, jumping; Sw, swimming; WH, walking-hopping.

FIGURE S7. Ancestral state reconstruction of PC2 for extant species shown as coloured branches. PC2 values derived from the PCA of the total dataset. Coloured bars at the tips represent the locomotor mode of each species. Abbreviations: J, jumping; Sw, swimming; WH, walking-hopping.

FIGURE S8. Ancestral state reconstruction of locomotor modes by Maximum Likelihood. Shown in a separate file.

FIGURE S9. Ancestral state reconstruction of locomotor modes by Parsimony. Shown in a separate file.